

Efficacy of botanicals in managing sheath rot (ShR) of rice

V. Narasimhan, V. V. Sridhar, and A. Abdul Kareem, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

The efficacy of neem derivatives and leaf extracts of *Prosopis juliflora* L. (10%) and *Ipomoea cornea* L. (10%) on ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw., was evaluated using susceptible cultivar Co 43 in the field in 1990-91 and 1991-92 wet seasons (WS). Neem derivatives were neem seed kernel extract 5% (NSKE), neem oil 3% (NO), and neem formulation 3% (NF) from Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. Leaf extracts and standard fungicide carbendazim (0.1%) were applied as foliar sprays at booting and 10 d later. Neem cake (NC) at 150 kg/ha and neem cake-coated urea (NCU) at 150 kg NC/ha + 75 kg N/ha were applied to the soil at planting. Each treatment was replicated three times. Plots were 5 × 4 m².

ShR incidence was measured as the percentage of tillers affected in 25

Effect of botanicals on ShR incidence and grain yield of rice.* Aduthurai, India. 1990-92 WS.

Treatment	Dose	Mean ShR (%)		Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
		1990-91	1991-92	1990-91	1991-92
Neem cake, basal	150 kg/ha	20.9 ab	- ^c	5.6 bc	-
Neem cake, basal + neem seed kernel extract 5% FS ^b	Neem cake at 150 kg/ha + FS 5%	18.2 a	-	6.2 a	-
Neem seed kernel extract - FS	5%	17.6 a	27.7 a	6.2 a	5.0 a
Neem cake-coated urea, basal	Neem cake at 150 kg/ha + urea at 75 kg N/ha	25.4 ab	-	6.0 ab	-
Neem oil - FS	3%	23.7 ab	29.4 a	5.6 bc	4.1 d
<i>Prosopis</i> leaf extract FS	10%	26.3 b	28.3 a	5.3 bc	4.7 abc
<i>Ipomoea</i> leaf extract FS	10%	23.9 ab	30.9 a	5.9 ab	4.5 bcd
Neem formulation	3%	-	29.0 a	-	4.5 cd
Carbendazim	0.1%	17.6 a	27.0 a	6.1 a	5.1 a
Untreated check	-	40.0 c	41.9 b	5.2 c	3.7 e

*Values after angular transformation. Values having a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bFS = foliar spray. ^cNot tested.

randomly selected hills per plot at 20 d after the last spray.

All treatments significantly reduced ShR in both years, (see table). NSKE alone, NC + NSKE, and carbendazim controlled ShR significantly better in the first year trial than in the second, which was reflected in grain yield. In the second

year, the carbendazim treatment recorded the highest grain yield, but did not significantly differ from NSKE and *Prosopis* leaf extract.

NSKE applied as foliar spray is promising for reducing ShR and increasing grain yield. ■

New races of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) among strains representing major rice-growing areas of India and Nepal

Faiz-Ur Rehman, Plant Pathology Department (PPD), University of Hawaii (UH), 3190 Maile Way, Honolulu, Hawaii 96822, USA; S. S. Gnanamanickam, Center for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600025, India; T. B. Adhikari, Plant Pathology Department, Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science, Central Campus, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal; and A. M. Alvarez, PPD, UH

We have studied the pathogenic variation of 122 *Xoo* strains (86 from India, 36 from Nepal) using IRRI's standard differential rice cultivars IR8 (*Xa-11*), IR20 (*Xa-4*), IR1545-339 (*xa-5*), CAS209 (*Xa-10*), and DV85 (*xa-5*, *Xa-7*). Strains were collected during the past 5 yr from various rice-growing areas in the Indian states of Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal,

and in the areas of Banke, Bara, Bardia, Bhairahawa, Butwal, Dang, Jhapa, Lamjung, Palpa, Parsa, Ratuhat, Syanja, and Tanahua of Nepal.

Plants of the differential cultivars were grown in a greenhouse at UH for 40-50 d. Suspensions of 24-48 h bacterial cultures were adjusted to 2 × 10⁸ colony forming units/ml. Plants were inoculated in replicated experiments using the scissor clip inoculation technique. Inoculated plants were kept under controlled conditions (28 °C temperature and 75% relative humidity) that favored both plant and disease development. Data on lesion lengths were recorded 14 d after inoculation, averaged, and rated as resistant or susceptible (see table).

One hundred twenty strains formed six groups based on average lesion length. Nepalese strains NXO200 and NXO216 did not fit any of the above pathogenicity patterns and were not assigned a group designation. None of the Nepalese strains tested corresponded to the previously reported race groups of N1 and N2 from

Nepal because they were not based on the rice differentials that we used in our study. Groups 1a, 1b, and 2 from the present study, however, corresponded to the previously reported Indian races Ia, Ib, and II, respectively. The reaction patterns of groups 3, 4, and 5 are new and have not been previously reported from these areas. Based on these findings, we are proposing to designate group 3, which included two Indian and eight Nepalese strains, as Indian race III, and the relatively small group 4, which included three Indian and one Nepalese strain, as Indian race IV. We have not assigned a race designation to the 11 Indian and 11 Nepalese low-virulence strains that formed group 5. If tested on some indigenous rice cultivars, this group of strains might be found virulent and have some significance. Notably, none of the 36 Nepalese strains tested belonged to Indian race Ib.

The discovery of two new races and a low virulence group may be useful in breeding for resistance against *Xoo* in India and Nepal. ■

Differential rice cultivar reactions to *Xoo* strains.

Group	Strain (no.)	Range of av lesion length and disease reaction ^a					Race designation
		IR8 (<i>Xa-11</i>)	IR20 (<i>Xa-4</i>)	IR1545-339 (<i>xa-5</i>)	CAS209 (<i>Xa-10</i>)	DV85 (<i>xa-5</i> , <i>Xa-7</i>)	
<i>Indian strains</i>							
	86						
Group 1a	5	13.0-28.0 (S)	3.0- 7.0 (R)	13.0-20.0 (S)	33.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 9.0 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	27	16.0-24.0 (S)	10.0-15.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	31.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 8.5 (R)	Ib
Group 2	38	19.0-23.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	17.0-21.0 (S)	20.0-39.0(S)	31.0-36.0 (S)	II
Group 3	2	10.0-18.0 (S)	3.0- 7.5 (R)	14.0-25.0 (S)	19.0-43.0 (S)	23.0-40.0 (S)	III
Group 4	3	11.0-23.0 (S)	3.0- 3.5 (R)	3.0- 9.0 (R)	23.0-46.0 (S)	6.0- 8.0 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.0- 3.5 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	3.0- 5.0 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	1.0- 5.0 (R)	-
<i>Nepalese strains</i>							
	36						
Group 1a	7	10.4-16.0 (S)	2.1- 7.7 (R)	10.3-21.7 (S)	10.5-24.6 (S)	3.0- 7.6 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	0	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(R)	Ib
Group 2	7	10.2-23.0 (S)	10.6-21.0 (S)	10.9-20.4 (S)	11.6-24.1 (S)	13.9-25.9 (S)	II
Group 3	8	10.9-21.3 (S)	1.8-6.3 (R)	13.0-19.6 (S)	14.8-19.3 (S)	14.8-22.1 (S)	III
Group 4	1	10.5 (S)	2.2 (R)	5.1 (R)	10.3 (S)	7.6 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.3- 8.4 (R)	1.0- 2.7 (R)	1.4- 6.1 (R)	2.2- 9.6 (R)	1.4- 9.4 (R)	-
NX0200	1	6.8 (R)	2.1 (R)	3.6 (R)	12.4 (S)	10.6 (S)	-
NX0216	1	10.5 (S)	5.5 (R)	7.5 (R)	10.8 (S)	13.6 (S)	-

^aR = resistant (<10-cm lesion length), S = susceptible (>10-cm lesion length).

Integrated pest management—insects

Effects of neem and nochi on rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta*

C. Durairaj, National Pulses Research Centre, Vamban Pudukkottai 622303 and M. S. Venugopal, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, India

We conducted a field experiment using IR20 to study the effects of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Vitex negundo* (nochi)

Effect of botanical pest control products on rice bug populations. Madurai, India, 1991-92.

Treatment	Rice bug (no./ 5 net sweeps) ^a	Decrease over control (%)
Malathion 0.05%	4.0	86.2
Neemark 0.5%	5.0	82.8
Neem oil 2.0%	9.0	69.0
Nochi leaf extract 2.5%	14.3	50.7
Nochi leaf extract 5.0%	18.0	38.0
Neem seed kernel extract 5.0%	17.7	39.0
Control	29.0	-
CD (P = 0.05)	2.54	

^aMean of three replications.

botanical pest control products on rice bug during the second season (Sep 1991-Feb 1992). The insecticide malathion 50 EC was included for comparison (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 20-m² plots and three replications.

Twenty-four hours after spraying, rice bug populations were assessed as the

Developmental biology and host plant range of rice-feeding tiger moth *Cretonotus gangis* (L.)

J. L. A. Catindig, A. T. Barrion, and J. A. Litsinger, IRRI

We studied the development of *C. gangis* on 20 common plant species from families Poaceae (14), Cyperaceae (5), and Commelinaceae (1). Unfed neonate larvae were placed on 25- to 30-d-old individual host plants in 20-cm-diam clay pots enclosed in 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with top and side vents of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Ten larvae were released per cage. Each cage served as a treatment, replicated 10 times, in a randomized complete block design in a

number of bugs/five sweeps of a net. Only four rice bugs were recorded in the malathion-sprayed plot, which had a population reduction of 86.2% compared with the control. The next best treatment was Neemark, with 5 bugs. Neem oil, neem seed kernel extract, and nochi were much less effective than malathion and Neemark. ■

non-airconditioned headhouse. Temperature averaged 26.9 ± 1.06 °C. Relative humidity averaged 73.2 ± 4.0%. Host suitability was determined as percentage of larval survival, larval developmental period, larval growth index, and eggs laid by emerging females.

Fecundity was determined on an individual basis for newly emerged moths, which were held in a 65- × 65- × 110-cm rectangular wooden cage frame with sides of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Honey solution (10%) was provided for food. A male was introduced for each caged female.

C. gangis survived to pupation on all 20 plant species, confirming the polyphagous nature of this insect.